

ACTIONS TO STRENGTHEN UKRAINIAN CULTURAL IDENTITY IN THE PARANA SCENARIO: PRESERVING MEMORY AND UKRAINIAN IDENTITY

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ABSTRACT. The project «Actions to Strengthen Ukrainian Cultural Identity in the Paraná Scenario» aimed to promote the Ukrainian culture in the state of Paraná, Brazil. The activities included lectures, debates, meetings with the Ukrainian community, and the organization of international conferences. The project reached over 500 people and contributed to: strengthening Ukrainian cultural identity among participants, increasing interest in the Ukrainian culture in the Paraná community, stimulating intercultural dialogue and the appreciation of cultural diversity, preserving the Ukrainian cultural memory and heritage in Paraná. The project was an important step towards the recognition of the Ukrainian culture in the state and contributed to intercultural dialogue and the preservation of cultural memory.

KEYWORDS: Ukrainian culture, cultural identity, memory, preservation, Paraná, Brazil.

Introduction

The project ACTIONS TO STRENGTHEN UKRAINIAN CULTURAL IDENTITY IN THE PARANAENSE SCENARIO, financed by the Araucária Foundation, had as its main objective to promote the appreciation and recognition of Ukrainian culture in the state of Paraná. Through various activities, the project sought to foster intercultural dialogue, strengthen ties between the Ukrainian community and Paraná society in general, and contribute to the preservation of Ukrainian memory and cultural legacy in the state.

The activities were developed by Visiting Professor, Doctor Svitlana Kryvoruchko, supervised by this author. In the process of strengthening cultural identity, the memory of a people plays a fundamental role. The recovery of this

memory and the development of actions for its preservation have a decisive impact on the self-perception of individual members of the community.

University Extension is a fundamental pillar of the triple mission of universities, alongside teaching and research. It is characterized as a dialogical and interactive process between academia and society, seeking social transformation through the dissemination of knowledge, the production of knowledge and the construction of solutions to community problems.

The Forum of Pro-Rectors of Extension (FORPROEX) defines Extension as «an educational, cultural and scientific process that articulates teaching and research with social reality, through transformative interaction between the University and the different segments of society» (FORPROEX, 2000, p. 5). This interaction takes place through various activities, such as:

- Courses and workshops (community training in various areas).
- Lectures and events (dissemination of knowledge and information).
- Extension projects (direct intervention in the community to solve problems)
- Technical advice (support for public and private entities)
- Cultural production (artistic and cultural manifestations).

University Extension seeks to achieve several objectives, including:

- Democratize access to knowledge.
- Promote social inclusion, combating social inequalities and promoting human and social development.
- Strengthen citizenship through community participation in public life and in the construction of a more just and democratic society.
- Produce knowledge through interaction with the community, responding to their demands and needs.
- Promote local and regional development, especially the socioeconomic situation of communities.

According to Freire, «extension, as an educational process, is not limited to the mere transfer of knowledge, but aims to discuss, with the people, their reality, to problematize it» (Freire, 1983, p. 114).

For Santos, «University Extension is a process of knowledge production that is built from the interaction between scientific knowledge and popular knowledge» (Santos, 2004, p. 29).

According to the Forum of Pro-Rectors of Extension (FORPROEX): «University Extension is an educational, cultural and scientific process that articulates teaching and research with social reality, through transformative interaction between the University and the different segments of society» (FORPROEX, 2000, p. 5).

University Extension also faces challenges, such as the need to overcome the traditional assistance model, to strengthen interdisciplinarity and articulation with teaching and research, to guarantee the quality of extension actions and to expand community participation (Dias Sobrinho, 2004).

From this perspective, this work aims to report the extension activities developed within the scope of the project, with the financial support of the Araucária Foundation (2022).

Methodology

The project was developed over 12 months, with various activities carried out, such as:

1. Lectures and debates: on the history of Ukrainian immigration in Paraná, Ukrainian culture and its contemporary challenges.

2. Meetings with ethnic Ukrainians, representatives of the Ukrainian diaspora in Brazil: October – Prudentópolis. Museum of Ukrainian Culture; November – Meeting with ethnic Ukrainians involved in honey production; meeting with representatives of the Ukrainian diaspora; discussion of the events of the Holodomor in Ukraine in 1933; December – Discussion about the Anderson Prado's book «A Fortaleza de Wira».

3. Preparation and organization of conferences – 3.1 – Organization of the Third International Scientific Conference, April 6th and 7th, 2023, whose title is «Arguments of modern philology: freedom and security. Institutions involved: Kharkiv HS Skovoroda National Pedagogical University, Kharkiv, Ukraine, and Central-West State University – UNICENTRO, Irati, Paraná, Brazil. 3.2 – Organization of the XV International Scientific-Experimental Congress «Professional and artistic translation:

theory, methodology, practice», from April 20 to 21, 2023. National Aviation University, Kyiv, Ukraine and Central-West State University – UNICENTRO, Irati, Paraná, Brazil. 3.3 – Organization of the 1st International Congress «Health and Human Security in Education and Through Education», from 18 to 19 May 2023. Kharkiv HS Skovorody National Pedagogical University, Kharkiv, Ukraine; UNICENTRO, Irati, Paraná, Brazil.

Results

The project ACTIONS TO STRENGTHEN UKRAINIAN CULTURAL IDENTITY IN THE PARANANA SCENARIO** achieved significant results, such as: participation of more than 500 people in the various activities carried out, strengthening of Ukrainian cultural identity among participants in the activities, increased interest in Ukrainian culture in the community of Paraná, encouragement of intercultural dialogue and the appreciation of cultural diversity, preservation of memory and the Ukrainian cultural legacy in Paraná.

Final considerations

The project ACTIONS TO STRENGTHEN UKRAINIAN CULTURAL IDENTITY IN THE PARANAENSE SCENARIO was an important step towards the appreciation and recognition of Ukrainian culture in the state. The activities carried out reached a significant audience and contributed to strengthening Ukrainian cultural identity among the participants.

The project also encouraged intercultural dialogue and the appreciation of cultural diversity, due to interaction with diasporas of other ethnicities. Furthermore, it contributed to the preservation of Ukrainian memory and cultural legacy in Paraná.

Thanks

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REFERENCES

Araucária Foundation. (2022). Public Call (CP) 10/2022.

Dias Sobrinho, J. (2004). Challenges of University Extension in Brazil. In: *Proceedings of the III Brazilian Congress of University Extension*. Florianópolis : Federal University of Santa Catarina.

FORPROEX. (2000). National University Extension Policy. Brasília : MEC/SESu.

Freire, P. (1983). *Extension or communication?* Rio de Janeiro : Peace and Land.

Santos, B. de S. (2004). *The University in the 21st Century: Towards a democratic and emancipatory reform of the University*. 2nd ed. São Paulo : Cortez.